

MWE survey

Start of Block: Welcome page & disclaimer

Thank you for considering participating in this survey!

Please read the following information carefully before participating.

1. This survey aims to gather knowledge on how Multi Word Expressions Lexicons (MWE lexicons) are used in research and language technologies to find and inform synergies between Lexicography and Natural Language Processing (NLP) in view of MWE identification and discovery. The survey's results will be disseminated in an open-access scientific publication.

This survey is carried out within the **UniDive Cost Action**, WG2 - Lexicon-Corpus Interface activities (<https://unidive.lisn.upsaclay.fr/>).

2. Participation in this survey involves answering questions on the use of MWE lexicons or vocabularies and on their characteristics. It is estimated to take approximately 15-25 minutes to complete.

3. The personal data collected and processed will be exclusively those required to achieve the mentioned goals. The requested personal information is necessary to determine your eligibility for the survey. No identification document or identification number will be requested. For survey application monitoring purposes, an email address will be asked. Email information will be kept for a maximum period of 6 months.

The legal basis for the processing of your personal data is your informed consent, as the data detainer. Therefore, we request that you understand this information and confirm your decision to participate in the survey.

4. After participation, your data will be safeguarded under the [General Data Protection Regulation](#). Data will be anonymized to prevent the identification of specific individuals through data cross-referencing. All reasonable measures will be taken to protect your data. You have the right to file a complaint with your national Data Protection Authority. The contacts of the National Data Protection Authorities in Europe can be consulted at https://edpb.europa.eu/about-edpb/about-edpb/members_en.

5. Your participation is voluntary. You can interrupt it at any time, without any consequences. If you wish to interrupt your participation, please inform us of your intention within 2 weeks after taking the survey through the email: raquelamaro@fcsh.unl.pt.

6. It is unlikely that participation in this survey involves disadvantages or risks. If you have any doubts, concerns, or dissatisfaction regarding your participation in the survey, please contact, Raquel Amaro, at raquelamaro@fcsh.unl.pt.

Thank you for considering participating in this survey!

End of Block: Welcome page & disclaimer

Start of Block: Informed consent

I have read and understood the information concerning the survey provided above, and I had the opportunity and means to clarify any doubts or concerns.

Yes, I confirm. (1)

I understand that my participation in the survey is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw it without providing any justification, at any moment, and within 2 weeks after taking the survey, by indicating my Response ID.

Yes, I confirm. (1)

I understand that any information I supply may be used in scientific and academic papers and communications. I understand that my personal data will be automatically anonymised and stored for a maximum of 6 months. The compiled data may be further reused for research purposes. Moreover, I understand that all reasonable measures will be taken to protect my data.

Yes, I confirm. (1)

I agree to participate in this survey.

Yes, I confirm. (1)

End of Block: Informed consent

Start of Block: Sociodemographic questions

Can you provide us an e-mail address so we can more easily monitor the responses and contact you for follow-up questions, if necessary?

- Yes, here is my e-mail: (7) _____
- No, I don't want to provide an e-mail address. (3)

Where do you develop your professional activity? Please select the relevant option(s).

- Corporate/private sector (1)
- Government/public sector (2)
- Education/academic sector (4)
- Non-profit/NGO sector (5)
- Self-employed/freelancer (6)
- Other: (7) _____
- I don't know/I don't want to answer. (3)
-

What is the area of your expertise? Please select the relevant option(s).

- Artificial Intelligence (15)
 - Computational linguistics (13)
 - Computer Aided Translation (5)
 - Content editing/monitoring (8)
 - Data Science (2)
 - Information Retrieval (14)
 - Language Technologies (4)
 - Machine Learning (12)
 - Machine Translation (6)
 - Natural Language Processing (1)
 - Publishing (7)
 - Other: (11) _____
 - I don't know/I don't want to answer. (3)
-

What is your role/function? Please select the relevant option(s).

- director/coordinator (1)
 - researcher/developer (2)
 - student/intern (4)
 - Other: (11) _____
 - I don't know/I don't want to answer. (3)
-

Are you a member of a specific community (e.g., UniDive, ENeL, EURALEX, etc.)?

- Yes (please indicate which): (11)

- No. (1)
- I don't know/I don't want to answer. (3)

End of Block: Sociodemographic questions

Start of Block: Specific questions

Have you worked with MWE lexicons or vocabularies for NLP tasks **in the last 5 years**?

- Yes. (1)
- No. (2)

Display these questions if Have you worked with MWE lexicons or vocabularies for NLP tasks in the last 5 years? = Yes.

Can you provide examples of the NLP tasks where these lexicons have been used (e.g., named entity recognition, parsing, machine translation, information extraction, terminology extraction, topic modeling, hate speech detection, etc.)?

Can you provide examples of applications where these lexicons have been used? Please describe and provide the link (if possible).

Can you provide more details about these lexicons?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

End of Block: Specific questions

Start of Block: Lexicon details 1

Display these questions if Can you provide more details about these lexicons? = Yes

Please fill in all the relevant characteristics:

- Name of the lexicon: (1) _____
- Link (if possible): (3) _____
- Citation (if possible): (4) _____
- Size (amount / size unit): (10) _____

Format:

- Printed (1)
- Electronic (2)
- Database (3)
- Other: (5) _____
- I don't know/I don't want to answer. (4)

Type:

- Monolingual (1)
- Bilingual (2)
- Multilingual (3)
- Other: (5) _____
- I don't know/I don't want to answer. (4)

Direction:

- Monodirectional (2)
- Bidirectional (3)
- Other: (5) _____
- I don't know/I don't want to answer. (4)
-

Language(s) coverage:

Access:

- Free (2)
- Paid (3)
- Licensed by: (6) _____
- Other: (5) _____
- I don't know/I don't want to answer. (4)
-

Updates:

- Anually (2)
- Every two years (3)
- Every five years (6)
- Every ten years (7)
- Every twenty years (8)
- Never (9)
- Other: (5) _____
- I don't know/I don't want to answer. (4)

Do you have any other lexicon to describe?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

End of Block: Lexicon details

Start of Block: Lexicon details 2...5 if Do you have any other lexicon to describe? = Yes

End of Block: Lexicon details 5

Start of Block: Final questions

Display these questions if Have you worked with MWE lexicons or vocabularies for NLP tasks in the last 5 years? = Yes.

Are there any specific features or characteristics of these lexicons that make them particularly useful for NLP tasks? If so, please list them.

Do these MWE lexicons supplement other resources? If yes, please provide examples and specify the resources used.

Are there any difficulties or challenges associated with the use of these lexicons in NLP tasks?

Have you worked with MWE lexicons for other tasks (e.g., quality monitoring, terminological checking, post-editing, ...)? Please indicate which:

How do you rate the effectiveness of these lexicons in enhancing the performance of NLP tasks?

- 1 - Not effective at all (4)
- 2 - Slightly effective (5)
- 3 - Moderately effective (6)
- 4 - Very effective (7)
- 5 - Extremely effective (8)
- I don't know/I don't want to answer. (9)

What specific benefits have you observed while using MWE lexicons in NLP tasks? (Please provide examples if possible)

In your opinion, what improvements could be made to existing MWE lexicons to enhance their usefulness in NLP tasks?

Are there any recommended guidelines for integrating or using these lexicons in the NLP systems within your community?

Please feel free to share any additional comments, suggestions, or insights related to the use of MWE lexicons in NLP tasks.

End of Block: Final questions
